

Assessment of the Awareness and Attitude of Emergency Physicians towards the use of Computed Tomography in patients with head injury in various hospitals in Anambra State, Nigeria

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Assessment of the Awareness and Attitude of Emergency Physicians towards the use of Computed Tomography in patients with head injury in various hospitals in Anambra State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The use of x-ray and computed tomography scan is critical in the management of traumatic conditions, particularly head injuries. This study was carried out to assess the level of awareness and attitude of Emergency physicians towards the use of CT in cases of head injury. A cross-sectional study was done among emergency physicians working in five different government hospitals in Anambra State. Among the respondents were 29% males and 4% females: mean age was 35.7 years while their modal age was 31-40 years. All the respondents, 33 (100%) stated they find CT scan as a useful diagnostic medical imaging modality. However less than half of them, 15 (45.5%) stated they refer patients for CT scan for those patients that need it. Whereas most of them, 20 (64.5%) stated that head injury patients should undergo both X-Ray and CT scan virtually all of them 32 (97%), responded that computed tomography, (CT) is better than skull x-ray in the examination of head injury. Though majority of the respondents 31 (93%), stated that CT scan subject the patient to some risks. All those who responded and thought that CT scan should continue to be used as medical diagnostic imaging modality were 33 (100%). The result of the study showed that most of the emergency physicians are aware of the usefulness of CT in the examination of patients presenting with head injury, but the non- availability and cost of services of the CT imaging equipment greatly affected the rate of request for the examination and has affected their attitude towards the use of this imaging modality in the examination of this category of patients in need of it.

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